

Investigations on the Adsorptive Property of Silica Gel. Part III. Volume Changes produced on Displacement of Adsorbed Liquids in Silica Gel by Water.

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It has been generally assumed that silica gel presents the same volume of capillary space for adsorption of various liquids, though in existing literature on the subject appreciable variations have been noticed by some workers (Holme, "Laboratory Manual of Colloid Chemistry," 1928, p. 195). The exact measurement of adsorption by the usual dynamic method is rather difficult owing to the condensation of the liquid outside the gel capillaries when air saturated with the vapour of the liquid is passed over the gel. The present paper describes the determination of volume changes produced on the displacement of adsorbed liquids in silica gel by water. The volume changes enable us to calculate the volumes of different liquids adsorbed per g. of the gel.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The silica gel used was a commercial product supplied by the Silica Gel Corporation. Its water content was 3.35%. The organic

FIG. 1.

For liquids lighter than H_2O .

FIG. 2.

For liquids heavier than H_2O .

liquids employed were purified and dried by the standard methods in organic chemistry. The volume changes were measured in the apparatus shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

For liquids lighter than water, the apparatus shown in Fig. 1, was employed. The bulb A had a capacity of 120 c.c. The calibrated capillary C, could be attached at G, by an interchangeable ground glass joint. The entire apparatus was first filled with air-free water. Stop-cocks S_1 and S_3 were closed while S_2 remained open. Water in A was then poured out and was dried well by prolonged evacuation using connection F. A weighed amount of the silica gel was introduced into A, through G, which was again fitted with the tube F, and evacuated for an hour. It was then filled with the air-free organic liquid (introduced through the funnel N) to the mark M. F was then replaced by the capillary C. The apparatus was immersed in a thermostat at $30^\circ \pm 0.005$ until the stop-cock S_2 was under water and the bulb A was completely filled with organic liquid to the mark N, on the capillary. After allowing the apparatus to attain the temperature of the thermostat, stop-cock S_2 was closed, S_1 opened and the reading taken. When the reading was constant, S_3 was opened to allow the water to wet the gel and the level in C was read. It was noticed that there was a large decrease at first followed by a slight rise as shown in Table I for a typical experiment. When the volume remained constant for 4 hours, the final reading was taken. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE I.

Time (min.)	...	15	30	45	60	75	120	600
Decrease in vol. (c.c.)	...	0.582	0.569	0.566	0.560	0.538	0.529	0.518

TABLE II.

Liquid.	Decrease in volume of the gel.	Average.	Correction for volume change on mixing the liquid with water in absence of the gel.
Benzene	0.00850 c.c./g. 0.00863	0.00807	Nil
Xylene	0.0109 0.0108	0.0109	Nil
Carbon tetra- chloride	0.0200 0.0198	0.0199	Nil
Nitro- benzene	0.017 0.0198	0.0198	0.007 c.c. per 20.5 g.
Aniline	0.00694		0.038 c.c. per 20.2 g.

The results obtained show clearly that silica gel takes up a larger volume of water than the liquids mentioned above. If in silica gel the capillary space available for occupation of liquids is to be considered constant, we have to assume that water is under great compression and further more that different liquids held in the gel capillaries are subjected to different pressures. It is more probable, however, that in silica gel there are certain fine capillaries which can be penetrated only by water but not by organic liquids and that different organic liquids have different organic penetrating powers, carbon tetrachloride being least active. Certain observations of Cude and Hullet (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 833) are of interest in this connection. They found that active charcoal had maximum density in water. The following results were obtained by them.

TABLE III

Density of charcoal.

Water	Benzene	Carbon tetrachloride
1.829 after 15 min.	1.794 after 15 min.	1.586 after 15 min.
1.854 ,, 119 hrs.	1.797 ,, 286 hrs.	1.647 ,, 386 hrs.

The differences in density are probably due to different penetrating powers.

The volumes of carbon tetrachloride and benzene absorbed per g. of the gel were determined by the dynamic method and found to be 0.8288 c.c. for benzene, and 0.3126 c.c. for carbon tetrachloride. The difference in volumes absorbed is 0.0092 c.c. per g. of the gel. This value compares favourably with the difference in volume decrease noticed in the displacement experiment (*vide*, Table III, $0.0199 - 0.00857 = 0.0113$ c.c. per g.).

Volume decrease caused when water displaces a mixture on silica gel.—For this investigation, a mixture of benzene and carbon tetrachloride was employed since it was not soluble in water. The experimental procedure was the same as in the previous case; instead of organic liquid, binary mixture was used. The results are tabulated below. The sample of the gel used was different from that employed in the previous experiment and gave a volume decrease of 0.0198 c.c. per g. of the gel when benzene was displaced by water.

TABLE IV.

Benzene in the mixture.	Vol. decrease.	Benzene in the mixture.	Vol. decrease.
100.0 %	0.0123 c.c./g.	34.6 %	0.0132 c.c./g.
92.4	0.0123	22.4	0.0139
77.5	0.0125	15.9	0.0146
60.0	0.0126	8.2	0.0160
51.3	0.0128	0.0	0.0200

The results are represented in Fig. 3. It is to be noticed that the slope of the curve is greatest at low concentrations of benzene.

FIG. 3.

DISCUSSION.

The defect in the dynamic method of measuring adsorption has already been pointed out. Using the displacement method, described in this paper we can calculate more accurately the volumes of different liquids adsorbed by silica gel, water being employed as the standard liquid. This method would be of particular value when dealing with liquids of low vapour pressure, for which the dynamic method is inapplicable (because the attainment of equilibrium is very slow).

Measurements by the displacement method are not practicable when the liquid dissolves in water producing large changes in volume. The volume decrease in the case of mixtures is of particular interest. If there had been no selective adsorption of benzene from its binary mixture with carbon tetrachloride, the volume decrease for 8% benzene mixture should have been 0.0193 c.c. while it is actually 0.0160 c.c. This shows considerable selective absorption of benzene at low concentrations (*cf.* B. S. Rao, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 616). Silica gel is to be considered to have a certain adsorption surface which can be occupied by benzene, but not by carbon tetrachloride. When benzene in 8% concentration is employed, nearly half of this reserved space gets occupied by benzene. At 22%, nearly 80% is similarly occupied. This accounts for the slope of the curve in Fig. 3.

SUMMARY.

1. The volume changes produced on displacement by water, of adsorbed liquids in silica gel has been measured using an apparatus specially devised for the purpose.
2. The displacement method described, enables one to calculate the volume of liquids adsorbed per g. of the gel.
3. Unlike the dynamic method, the new technique is applicable to non-volatile liquids.
4. The method has also been used to measure the decrease in volume on the displacement by water, of binary mixtures adsorbed by the gel and the significance of the results obtained has been discussed.